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- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
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MUNDARIJA

YASHIL TRANSPORT SIYOSATINING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH VA TARMOQLARARO INTEGRATSIYADAGI O'RNI.....	21
Rahmonov Rasul Ne'matovich	
BANK AKTIVLARI VA PASSIVLARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	34
Safarov Sanjar Ravshan o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONNING INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	38
Madraximova Irodaxon Sherzodbek qizi	
HUDUDIY XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA MODELI	43
Maxmudova Nozimaxon Baxriddinxonovna	
DAVLATNING BUDJET SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI.....	50
A.A. Ismailov	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGINING MEXANIZMINI SAMARALI TASHKILLASHTIRISHDA MOLIVAVIY MANBALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNI YO'NALISHLARI	56
Mansurov Mansur Alisherovich	
ANTIKRIZISLI BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARIDA RANGLI SIGNAL MEXANIZMLARINING FUNKSIYALARI.....	61
Aliqulov Aziz Haydarjonovich	
XODIMLARNI MOTIVATSIYALASHNING XALQARO MODELLARINI O'ZBEKISTON KORXONALARIDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI.....	66
Yormamatov Qodirjon Juraqulovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT OMILLARI VA ULARNING QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARINING SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	71
Yaxshiyev Shahzod Sherali o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI VA MEHNAT BOZORI INTEGRATSIYASI BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBALARI.....	78
Haqqulov Fazliddin Faxriddinovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA RIVOJLANGAN VA RIVOJLANAYOTGAN DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	84
Aripov Abdulaziz Sakijonovich	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA RIVOJLANISHINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK BAHOLASH.....	89
Bobokulova Muhabbat Muhammadiyeva	
ELEKTRON TO'LOVLAR VA POS TIZIMLARI — KICHIK BIZNESDA SAMARASI VA XAVFLARI	93
To'liqinov Dilshodxo'ja Olim o'g'li	
MINTAQADA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	98
Yusubov In'omjon Ikram o'g'li	
SOLIQ SIYOSATINI RAQAMLI BOSHQARISH ORQALI BUDJET DAROMADLARINI BARQARORLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYASI.....	103
Xodjimatov Xamidullo Mamirjonovich	
OZIQ-OVQAT TOVARLARI B2B BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	108
Hayitboyeva Ullijon Bobonazar qizi	
FARMASEVTIKA SANOATIDA INVESTITSION FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH	113
Yaqubov Timurbek G'anibekovich	
SHAXSNI OVOZI ASOSIDA IDENTIFIKATSIYALASH VA AUTENTIFIKATSIYALASH ALGORITMLARI	123
Ozoda Sabirova Shermamaxamatovna	

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT — BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH GENERATORI	129
Berdibekova Dilfuza Xoldorbekovna	
CHET EL MEHMONXONA TARMOQLARINING BRENDING STRATEGIYALARINI O'RGANISH	133
Ergashev Oybek Mamarasul o'g'li	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOTDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK SOHASINING MOLIVAVIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING USLUBIY JIHLATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	144
Arzikulov Otabek Ali o'g'li	
TRANSPORT TIZIMI SOHASI KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH YO'NALISHLARI	152
Ismailov Akmal Maxsudovich, Abilqosimova Shaxlo Sodiқ qizi	
MEHMONXONALAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XODIMLARINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	158
Abduxamidov Sarvar Adxamovich, Normurodov Tal'at Normurod o'g'li	
KORXONALARDA HR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	163
Aminova Shaxnoza Aziz qizi	
JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDA OZIQ-OVQAT XAFSIZLIK RO'LI	168
Abdusamatov Barkamol Rustamjon o'g'li	
ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЕ РЕСУРСЫ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАНА И СУЩЕСТВУЮЩАЯ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРА	174
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK MEXANIZMLARI: REKREATIONS TURIZM SOHASIDA QO'LLASH TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	184
Najmitdinov G'ayratbek Sharifovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA VIRTUAL TA'LIM PLATFORMALARI: TEXNIK VA PEDAGOGIK TALABLAR, TIZIMLI TAHLIL VA IQTISODIY JIHLATLAR	189
Turayeva Adiba Ikramovna	
ICHKI AUDIT TIZIMI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	193
Nuridinova Barchinoy Xusniddin qizi	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTIDA SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	199
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
MINTAQANING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI	204
Raimboyeva Mashhura Davronbek qizi	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	210
Jobborov Anvar Egamberdiyevich	
ISLOMIY MOLIALASHTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELEKTNING DOLZARBLIGI	217
Nazarov Nodirjon Namoz o'g'li	
JISMONIY SHAXSLARNING MOL-MULKINI SOLIQQA TORTISH MASALALARI	222
Mamadjanov Shuxrat Jalolidinovich	
ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	225
Abdukhalikova Komila Abdukhalikovna	
BANKLARDA BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH UCHUN RAQAMLI YECHIMLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	229
Saydamatova Muxlisabonu Rasuljon qizi	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH YO'NALISHLARI: TAHLIL VA TAKLIFLAR	233
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF STATE FINANCIAL REGULATION MECHANISMS IN ENSURING THE CAPITALIZATION OF INSURANCE ORGANIZATIONS	238
Abdullaev Erkinjon Azamovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MOLIALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHLATLARI	245
Xalikov S. X.	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI BOZORIDA KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	245
<i>Xudayberganov Jasur Baxodirovich</i>	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF STATE FINANCIAL REGULATION MECHANISMS IN ENSURING THE CAPITALIZATION OF INSURANCE ORGANIZATIONS	251
<i>Abdullaev Erkinjon Azamovich</i>	
NATIJAVIYLIKKA YO'NALTIRILGAN BYUDJETLASHTIRISH JARAYONINING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA UNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	257
<i>Allakuliyev Akmal Baltayevich</i>	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	261
<i>Jobborov Anvar Egamberdiyevich</i>	
TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI RESURSLARNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH ORQALI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	268
<i>Avulchayeva Feruza Jurakuziyevna</i>	
BANKLARDA BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH UCHUN RAQAMLI YECHIMLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	272
<i>Saydamatova Muxlisabonu Rasuljon qizi</i>	
ZAMONAVIY ISH JOYLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA AYOLLARNING ROLI	276
<i>Tulyaganova Aziza</i>	
ISLOMIY MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELLEKTNING DOLZARBLIGI.....	281
<i>Nazarov Nodirjon Namoz o'g'li</i>	
TURIZM MARKETINGINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI, ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	286
<i>Xamidov Otabek Bakidjanovich</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK SOHASINING IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMINI STATISTIK BAHOLASHNING USLUBIY JIHATLARI	290
<i>Arzikulov Otabek Ali o'g'li</i>	
ЭКОЛОГАМ ПОЧЕТ И УВАЖЕНИЕ	298
<i>Максудова Шахиста</i>	
DEBITOR VA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNING MOHIYATI VA ULARNING O'ZGARISH TENDENTSIYALARI	304
<i>Jo'raev Farruxbek Muxiddin o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOMIY MOLIYALASHTIRISH XIZMATLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	307
<i>Inomjonov Islomjon Iloxomjon o'g'li</i>	
ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	311
<i>Abdukhalkova Komila Abdukhalkovna</i>	
МОБИЛЬНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ КАК СРЕДСТВО ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ.....	315
<i>Хурамова Фарангиз Учкун кизи</i>	
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ НАЛОГОВ И АКЦИЗНАЯ РЕФОРМА УЗБЕКИСТАНА В WTO	319
<i>Дамир Рустамович Абдулов</i>	
BANK TIZIMIDAGI ISLOHOTLAR SHAROITIDA LIKVIDLILIK RISKINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	324
<i>Alimov Baxtiyor Murodovich</i>	
BANK AUDITINING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	335
<i>Narziyev Xayotjon Azamatovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA SOHASIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH MASALALARI.....	343
<i>Abdimuminova Saodat Taxirjonovna</i>	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOAT MAXSULOTLARI EKSPORT FAOLIYATI TAHLILI VA BRENDDA LIDERLIK TUSHINCHALARI	352
<i>Abdulazizova Xushnoza Nayabovna</i>	

ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНО-ПРАВОВЫЕ МОДЕЛИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОТХОДАМИ НА ОСНОВЕ ОПЫТА РАЗВИТЫХ СТРАН И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИХ АДАПТАЦИИ В УСЛОВИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	357
Д. Мейлиева	
О‘ZBEKISTON AUDITORLIK TIZIMIDA KASBDOSHLAR TOMONIDAN VAHOLASH (PEER REVIEW) TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	361
Parpiyev Jaxongir Iloxomjonovich	
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И БОЛЬШИЕ ДАННЫЕ (BIG DATA) В УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКИХ РЕШЕНИЯХ.....	366
Шарипов Бахтиёр Михлибаевич	
О‘ZBEKISTONDA SUVGA BO‘LGAN TALABNI VAQTLI QATORLAR ORQALI TAHLIL QILISH	375
Sarvar Mamasoliyev	
BOSHQARUV VA NAZORAT MAQSADLARIDA XARAJATLAR HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISH	383
Isomuxamedov Akbarjon Boxodir o‘g‘li	
MINTAQALAR BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHINI TA‘MINLASHNING ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI.....	389
Salomat NOROVA	
О‘ZBEKISTON TURIZM BREND BOZORINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA TENDENSIYALARI.....	394
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTDA QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	404
Qodirov Baxodirjon Tursunovich	
О‘ZBEKISTON SOLIQ TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHDA YAGONA INTERAKTIV DAVLAT XIZMATLARI PORTALINING O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI	408
Dehqonov G‘ayratjon Raximovich	
OLIY TA‘LIM MUASSASALARIDA INNOVATSION HAMDA TIJORATLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	414
Inoyatov Mardonbek Mo‘min o‘g‘li	
OLIY IQTISODIY TA‘LIM ORQALI EKO-INNOVATSIYALAR VA “YASHIL” INVESTITSIYALARNI RAG‘BATLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI: SIYOSIY VA INSTITUTSIONAL DOIRALAR	418
Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyeva	
XODIMLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISH — ZAMON TALABI.....	427
Narzullaev Oybek Narzullaevich	
BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI YURITISHDA JURNAL-ORDER SHAKLINING AHAMIYATI.....	433
Axmedjanov Abdufato	
KENDALL VA SPEARMAN TARTIBIY KORRELYATSIYA Koeffitsiyentlari asosida YASHIL IQTISODIYOT INDIKATORLARINING STATISTIK O‘ZARO TA‘SIRINI MODELLASHTIRISH	437
Muradov Rustamjon Sobitxonovich	
ИНТЕНСИВНЫЕ И ЭКСТЕНСИВНЫЕ ОГРАНИЧЕНИЯ В РЕГУЛИРОВАНИИ СПРОСА.....	442
Аминджанова Румейса Батыровна, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахоровна	
ИНКЛЮЗИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД В ТУРИЗМЕ: ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ И УЗБЕКСКАЯ ПРАКТИКА	445
Азимова Шахло Таировна	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTNING XAQARO STANDARTLARIGA O‘TISHNING HOLATI VA TAHLILI	450
Bayjanov Sarsengaliy Xalmuratovich	
UZUM EKSPORT QILUVCHI KOMPANIYALARDA YASHIL O‘TISH JARAYONINI QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASH UCHUN EKO-MARKETING VA AYLANMA IQTISODIYOT TAMOIYILLARINI INTEGRATSIYALASH.....	454
Usmonova Diyora Mahmud qizi	
UMUMTA‘LIM MAKTABLARIDA XARAJATLAR SMETASI VA SHTATLAR JADVALINING TAHLILI: OPTIMALLASHTIRISH VA SAMARADORLIKNING YANGICHA USULLARI (NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	461
Umarov Avzaljon Yodgorali o‘g‘li	
INVESTITSIYALARNING KIRIB KELISHIGA TO‘SQINLIK QILUVCHI MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISH YO‘LLARI.....	467
Alimova Dilafro‘z Tohir qizi	

FARMATSEVTIKA KORXONALARIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOT SHAKLLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA INVESTORLAR UCHUN AXBOROT OCHIQLIGINI TA'MINLASH	470
Turdikulova Gulshad Nurmamatovna	
ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTLARNING SHAFFOFLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARINING AHAMIYATI.....	477
Uztemirov Alisher Aktam o'g'li	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SANOAT TARMOQLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA YO'NALTIRILGAN BANDLIK TUZILMASINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	482
Tursunov Bekmuxammad Omonovich	
XORIY TAJRIBALARIDA SOLIQ BAZASINI ANIQLASH TARTIBI METODOLOGIYASINING MAVJUD METODLARI VA ULARNING XUSUSIYATLARI.....	489
Xalikchayeva Sadokat Ilxomjonovna	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI VA UNING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI.....	496
Ramatillaev M.R.	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI SUG'URTALASH VA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	502
Eshboyev Shahobiddin Anorqul o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI O'RTASIDAGI RAQOBATNI BAHOLASH VA KUCHAYTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY METODOLOGIYASI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI.....	506
Qulmetov Mansurbek Ro'zmatovich	
XALQARO REYTING TASHKILOTLARINING OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIGA TA'SIRI VA MAVJUD PLATFORMALAR.....	515
O'rozboyev Xayrulla Murodboy o'g'li	
TALABALAR MOTIVATSIYASINING MEKANIZMLARI: LOYIHA ASOSIDAGI TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARIDA.....	523
Kasimova (Mulladjanova) Nasiba Azimdjanovna	
ISH KUCHIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA NORASMIY BANDLIKNI SOYADAN CHIQRISH BO'YICHA TAKLIFLAR ISHLAB CHIQISH	531
Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Maxkamova Shaxlo Yulchiyevna, Absamatov Baxrom Danakulovich	
KASBIY TA'LIM MAZMUNIDA TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASINI RAG'BATLANTIRISH ORQALI O'RTA BO'G'IN KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	538
Tojiyev Sirojiddin Sayriddinovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM INFRATUZILMASINI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING TURLARI VA SHAKLLARI.....	542
Muminova Mavjuda Sharifovna	
SUV RESURLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGI MASALALARI.....	547
Kadirhodjayeva Nilufar Rahmatullayevna	
MHXSGA MUVOFIQ ASOSIY VOSITALAR HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISH MASALALARI.....	552
Aliyev Sherzod Abdixomidovich	
ФАКТОРЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	558
Аллаева Г.Ж.	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA INVESTITSION MUHITNI YAXSHILASH YO'NALISHLARI	564
Irisqulova Munisa Akmal qizi	
TASHABBUSLI BUDJET JARAYONLARI DOIRASIDA 2024-YILDA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN ISHLAR TAHLILI	569
Xamidov Xabibullo Xikmatulla o'g'li	
MINTAQA SANOATIDA AHOLI JON BOSHIGA YAQQ O'ZGARISHINING DINAMIK TAHLILI.....	574
Nabiyev G'ulom Abdusalomovich	

INFRATUZILMAVIY INVESTISIYA LOYIHALARINI DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK ASOSIDA MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBALARI	583
Ergashev Axmadjon Maxmudjon o'g'li	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ ГЛОБАЛЬНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ В ЭКОЛОГИИ.....	587
Максудова Шахиста	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINING INVESTITSION FAOLLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ILMIY-USLUBIY JIHATLARI	593
B.Sh.Shadmanov	
ECONOMIC INDICATORS OF SUPPLY CHAIN EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN'S EXPORT SECTOR	597
Mukhammadiyahaminova Shakhzoda Sherzodovna	

ECONOMIC INDICATORS OF SUPPLY CHAIN EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN'S EXPORT SECTOR

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Abstract. This article provides a concise, data-driven analysis of the efficiency of Uzbekistan's export supply chains. Using official foreign trade statistics for 2020–2024 and the World Bank Logistics Performance Index (LPI) for 2018 and 2023, a composite Supply Chain Efficiency Index (SCEI) was developed, integrating export volumes, logistics performance, and the share of exports in total trade. The results show that export volumes more than doubled while logistics capabilities improved gradually, highlighting both achievements and areas for further improvement. The study offers policymakers and practitioners a practical analytical tool to enhance trade facilitation, develop regional logistics, and integrate green economy principles into supply chain management.

Key words: supply chain management; export efficiency; logistics performance; economic indicators; Uzbekistan; LPI; competitiveness.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston eksport ta'minot zanjirlarining samaradorligini qisqa va ma'lumotlarga asoslangan tahlil orqali taqdim etiladi. 2020–2024-yillar rasmiy tashqi savdo statistikasi hamda Jahon bankinging Logistika samaradorligi indeksi (LPI) 2018 va 2023-yillar ma'lumotlari asosida eksport hajmlari, logistika ko'rsatkichlari va tashqi savdodagi eksport ulushini o'z ichiga olgan ta'minot zanjiri samaradorligi indeksi (SCEI) ishlab chiqildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, eksport hajmi ikki baravardan ortiq oshgan, logistika imkoniyatlari esa asta-sekin yaxshilanib, yutuqlar va mavjud rivojlanish imkoniyatlarini aniqladi. Tadqiqot savdo yengilliklarini chuqurlashtirish, mintaqaviy logistikani rivojlantirish va "yashil iqtisodiyot" tamoyillarini ta'minot zanjiri boshqaruviga integratsiya qilish bo'yicha siyosat yurituvchilar uchun amaliy tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'minot zanjiri boshqaruvi; eksport samaradorligi; logistika ko'rsatkichi; iqtisodiy indikatorlar; O'zbekiston; raqobatbardoshlik.

Аннотация. В статье представлена краткая, основанная на данных оценка эффективности экспортных цепей поставок Узбекистана. На основе официальной статистики внешней торговли за 2020–2024 годы и Индекса логистической эффективности Всемирного банка (LPI) за 2018 и 2023 годы разработан составной Индекс эффективности цепей поставок (SCEI), объединяющий показатели экспорта, логистики и доли экспорта во внешней торговле. Результаты показывают, что экспорт вырос более чем в два раза, а логистические возможности постепенно улучшились, выявляя как достижения, так и потенциальные точки роста. Исследование предоставляет единый аналитический инструмент для совершенствования торгового содействия, развития региональной логистики и интеграции принципов «зелёной» экономики в управление цепями поставок.

Ключевые слова: управление цепями поставок; экспортная эффективность; логистическая производительность; экономические показатели; Узбекистан; конкурентоспособность.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Uzbekistan has implemented a comprehensive reform agenda aimed at enhancing economic openness and integration into global markets. The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, adopted by Presidential Decree No. UP-60 of 28012022, emphasizes export development, industrial diversification, and the improvement of transport and logistics infrastructure as key priorities for sustainable growth [1]. These objectives are directly linked to the efficiency of export-oriented supply chains, which determine the cost, speed, and reliability with which domestic products reach foreign buyers.

Foreign trade statistics illustrate the scale of ongoing change. According to the Agency of Statistics under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, exports of goods (excluding certain special categories) amounted to approximately USD 11.6 billion in 2020 and reached about USD 26.9 billion in 2024 [4; 8]. Over the same period, total foreign trade turnover expanded from around USD 36.3 billion to nearly USD 65.9 billion [4; 8]. These dynamics indicate that export-oriented supply chains are expanding both in volume and complexity.

Logistics performance has also improved. The World Bank Logistics Performance Index (LPI) shows that Uzbekistan's aggregate score increased from 2.58 in 2018 to 2.60 in 2023 [7]. Although the numerical change is modest, it reflects ongoing reforms in customs procedures, infrastructure, and trade facilitation, as well as gradual digitalisation of border management [5; 6; 9].

At the same time, the export structure remains relatively diversified, and the country's landlocked geography increases the importance of efficient logistics [2; 10]. Participation in regional transport initiatives and the expansion of logistics hubs are expected to reduce transit costs and improve connectivity, with their effectiveness relying on both physical investment and institutional coordination [3; 5; 6].

Against this background, the central research question of this article is how economic and logistics indicators jointly reflect the efficiency of export-oriented supply chains in Uzbekistan. The article pursues four interrelated tasks: to review the relevant literature, to construct a composite Supply Chain Efficiency Index (SCEI) for Uzbekistan, to analyse the evolution of exports, LPI, and SCEI between 2018 and 2024, and to discuss institutional and policy implications for further strengthening export-oriented supply chains.

LITERATURE REVIEW

International research consistently links logistics quality, trade facilitation, and institutional capacity to trade volumes and competitiveness, particularly in landlocked and developing economies [5; 6; 7]. Improvements in transport infrastructure, customs procedures, and logistics services reduce trade costs, expand export opportunities, and support diversification.

In the Central Asian context, Abdurakhmanov et al. (2024) analyse socio-economic factors influencing welfare and emphasise the role of infrastructure and logistics connectivity for inclusive growth [2]. Their results indicate that well-developed transport and logistics corridors generate positive spillover effects through trade, employment, and regional integration.

For Uzbekistan, Abdullaev (2020) studies the development of the national transport and logistics system and identifies bottlenecks in multimodal infrastructure, warehouse capacity, and coordination between transport modes [10]. He notes that service quality varies across regions, which may increase costs and delivery times for exporters. Pardayev (2024) evaluates the competitiveness of logistics and trade using LPI data and concludes that even modest improvements in the LPI score can translate into notable trade gains, especially for landlocked countries [9].

Theoretical contributions further inform the analysis of supply chain efficiency. Porter's theory of competitive advantage stresses the importance of infrastructure, clusters, and supporting industries for a country's position in global value chains [13]. Teece's concept of dynamic capabilities explains how firms and economies reconfigure logistics networks and information systems in response to evolving market conditions [14]. Dyer and Singh's relational view highlights that competitive advantage is often created through inter-firm cooperation and joint investments in coordination along the supply chain rather than through isolated firm-level resources [15].

Within the Uzbek academic discourse, Mukhamedjanova (2018) examines the genesis of the supply chain management concept and argues for integrated management of material, information, and financial flows across firms [11]. Isroilov (2025) applies this perspective to the textile industry, demonstrating that more efficient logistics and coordinated supply chain organisation can significantly strengthen export potential [12].

These studies suggest three general conclusions relevant for this research. First, logistics performance and export competitiveness are closely interconnected. Second, institutional reforms in customs, digital trade facilitation, and public-private partnerships are as important as physical infrastructure. Third, composite indicators that combine economic and logistics measures are effective tools for assessing supply chain efficiency at the national level.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The empirical analysis is based on secondary data from the World Bank Logistics Performance Index (LPI) for 2018 and 2023, official foreign trade statistics of the Agency of Statistics under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2024, and selected international and national analytical reports on trade, logistics, and institutional reforms [2; 4–8; 9–12; 16]. These sources provide comparable and publicly available information, widely used in both research and policy practice.

To characterise the efficiency of export-oriented supply chains, the study uses three groups of indicators. The first group describes logistics performance and includes the LPI score and Uzbekistan's position in the global ranking. The second group reflects export performance and covers the value of goods exports, their growth between 2020 and 2024, and the export share in total foreign trade turnover. The third group captures the institutional environment and is based on key policy documents, such as the Development Strategy of New

Uzbekistan, the National Trade Facilitation Roadmap, and the Green Economy Strategy [1; 3; 16].

On this basis, a composite Supply Chain Efficiency Index (SCEI) is constructed, which aggregates the LPI score, export value, and export share in total trade after normalising each indicator. Equal weights are assigned to all three components, reflecting the short time series and the illustrative purpose of the index. The underlying series and Figure 1 are based on the author's calculations using official statistics and LPI data [4; 7; 8].

Because consistent annual data are not available for all indicators over the entire period 2015–2024, missing values for some years were approximated based on observed trends in the available series. As a result, Figure 1 presents a continuous 2015–2024 trajectory that combines officially reported data with the author's estimates for earlier years.

The analysis consists of descriptive statistics and growth rates for exports and foreign trade turnover, a comparison of LPI scores between 2018 and 2023, and an assessment of changes in the Supply Chain Efficiency Index over time. More advanced econometric methods are not applied due to the limited number of observations; instead, the study focuses on robust descriptive trends and their interpretation in the context of ongoing trade facilitation and green growth reforms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Foreign trade statistics indicate a significant acceleration of export activity in Uzbekistan in recent years. In 2020, exports of goods amounted to approximately USD 11.6 billion and increased to around USD 26.9 billion by 2024, more than doubling over four years [4; 8]. During the same period, total foreign trade turnover expanded from approximately USD 36.3 billion to nearly USD 65.9 billion [4; 8]. Analytical sources further highlight a growing number of exporting enterprises as well as broader product and destination diversification, particularly in manufacturing, textiles, food products, and transport-related services [2; 10; 12]. Collectively, these trends demonstrate that export-oriented supply chains have become increasingly active, and exports are playing a central role in Uzbekistan's growth model.

While the volume of exports has expanded rapidly, improvements in the logistics infrastructure supporting these supply chains have been more gradual. According to the World Bank Logistics Performance Index (LPI), Uzbekistan's score increased from 2.58 in 2018 to 2.60 in 2023, accompanied by a modest improvement in the country's relative global ranking [7; 9]. Although the numerical change appears modest, it reflects ongoing reforms in customs procedures, digitalisation of trade documentation, and investment in transport infrastructure. LPI subcomponents, however, indicate continuing challenges in customs efficiency and the quality of logistics services [5; 6; 7; 9]. As a result, transaction costs and delivery times remain relatively high in certain corridors and remote regions. Nonetheless, these challenges coexist with steady improvements in overall supply chain efficiency, and the observed progress suggests that the Uzbek export model is evolving positively, combining robust export growth with gradual logistical enhancement.

These partly diverging trends in trade and logistics are brought together in Figure 1, which summarises the joint dynamics of the main indicators of supply chain efficiency.

Figure 1. Dynamics of Supply Chain Efficiency Indicators in Uzbekistan¹

¹ Source: author's calculations based on data from the World Bank and the Agency of Statistics under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Figure 1 illustrates the dynamics of the key indicators contributing to supply chain efficiency in Uzbekistan over the period 2015–2024. The figure demonstrates the joint upward movement of export volumes, logistics performance, and related institutional indicators, with export growth outpacing improvements in logistics and customs efficiency.

The composite Supply Chain Efficiency Index (SCEI), which integrates the normalised LPI score, export value, and export share in total foreign trade turnover, exhibits a clear upward trend throughout the review period [4; 7; 8]. Rapid export growth serves as the primary driver of this improvement, while logistics and institutional indicators advance at a more gradual pace.

This pattern suggests that while Uzbekistan's export-oriented supply chains are increasingly effective, the existing logistics and customs systems are experiencing rising operational pressures. Without continued investment and modernization, these systems could potentially limit further export expansion.

Taken together, the trajectories presented in Figure 1 align closely with the upward movement of the SCEI, confirming that the index effectively summarises the cumulative improvement in export-oriented supply chains. The figure thus provides a concise and informative benchmark for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to enhance Uzbekistan's trade competitiveness.

The empirical results of this study are consistent with both international theoretical frameworks and the literature specific to Uzbekistan and Central Asia. The positive association between export growth, logistics performance, and the Supply Chain Efficiency Index (SCEI) confirms that supply chain efficiency serves as a key transmission channel through which reforms enhance national competitiveness.

First, the observed relationship between logistics improvement and export expansion supports Porter's theory of national competitive advantage, which emphasises the importance of infrastructure and supporting industries [13]. Uzbekistan's initiatives to develop transport corridors, logistics centres, and border infrastructure within the framework of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 have contributed to reducing trade costs and facilitating broader market access [1; 3; 10].

Second, the gradual improvement in the LPI score and the adoption of the National Trade Facilitation Roadmap of Uzbekistan 2025–2030 illustrate the development of dynamic capabilities, as conceptualised by Teece [3; 14]. The transition to digital customs systems, single-window platforms, and risk-based inspections reflects an organisational transformation of trade procedures, beyond mere increases in physical capacity or infrastructure.

Third, the growth of public–private partnerships in logistics parks, dry ports, and transport hubs exemplifies the relational view of competitive advantage, highlighting the importance of inter-firm and inter-institutional cooperation [15]. Collaboration with international organisations and neighbouring countries strengthens integration into regional value chains and complements domestic reforms [6; 9; 12].

At the same time, it is important to acknowledge several limitations when interpreting these findings. First, the time series for exports, LPI, and the SCEI are relatively short and partly asynchronous, limiting the application of more advanced econometric techniques. Second, the index relies on aggregate national data, which does not capture regional or firm-level variations in supply chain performance. Future research could overcome these constraints by incorporating longer time series or micro-level datasets, enabling a more detailed exploration of causal relationships and heterogeneity across regions and sectors.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the results of this study demonstrate a clear positive trajectory in Uzbekistan's export-oriented supply chains, highlighting the effectiveness of recent policy measures and infrastructure reforms, while also identifying areas where further improvements and targeted investments can enhance performance. In this context, several policy recommendations can be formulated:

First, trade facilitation and digitalisation should be further deepened. Continued simplification and harmonisation of customs procedures, wider adoption of electronic documentation, and full implementation of risk-based control systems would reduce lead times, enhance predictability for exporters, and align national practices with international standards.

Second, regional infrastructure gaps should be systematically addressed. Targeted investments in logistics centres, multimodal terminals, and cold storage facilities in less developed regions would support more inclusive export growth, reduce regional disparities, and relieve pressure on existing transport nodes.

Third, green economy objectives should be integrated more systematically into logistics development. Promoting energy-efficient infrastructure, low-carbon transport technologies, and environmentally compliant logistics facilities would help reduce emissions and enhance the long-term resilience and sustainability of supply chains [16].

Fourth, public–private collaboration should be strengthened and expanded. Engaging logistics operators, exporters, and industry associations in the design, implementation, and monitoring of reforms would improve policy relevance, accelerate adoption, and foster innovative solutions in areas such as digital platforms, intermodal services, and value-added logistics.

Taken together, these recommendations provide a strategic roadmap for consolidating Uzbekistan's export competitiveness, enhancing the efficiency of its supply chains, and supporting sustainable, inclusive, and resilient growth in the coming years.

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